

CLASSIFICATION OF ACADEMIC WORDS FOUND IN THE WORKS OF RESEARCHERS: A LITERATURE REVIEW

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Abstract.

An extensive vocabulary is one of the main factors for successful language learning. Consequently, the deeper a learner progresses in learning a language, the more sophisticated their vocabulary becomes. Sooner or later, this results in a learner being exposed to more advanced, infrequently used and specific words. Academic vocabulary ‘is indisputably one of the most prominent qualities of academic texts’ (Therova, 2020), which makes it an integral part of EAP studies. Various linguists use different lists and methods of classifying the vocabulary which can be treated as ‘academic’. Most frequently used terms for the list of academic words are “*Academic Word List*” (AWL) and “*Academic Vocabulary List*” (AVL). Some seem to favour the former, whilst others tend to regard the latter as more significant. The objectives of this study were to review the terminology used by different linguists, to consider the methods of selection of words to be included in the Academic Word/Vocabulary List and to consider the scope of academic vocabulary in texts, including their role in the study of language.

Key words: AWL, AVL, academic, terminology, classification, high-frequency words, low-frequency words.

Introduction.

This study has reviewed published and reviewed articles by Charles & Pecorari (2016), Therova (2020), Hartshorn & Hart (2016), Coxhead (2011), and Masrai & Milton (2018), describing English vocabulary from an academic, general or technical vocabulary discourse. The paper provides a comparison of the studies and methodologies of given linguists. Notwithstanding the fact that in these articles the authors use different terms, references to each other's work, similarities in views or research conclusions can also be found. This study will point out such differences and similarities in methodologies, approaches, and conclusions.

Terminology.

According to *Charles & Pecorari (2016)*, all the words used in academic texts can be divided into these three categories.

- general,
- academic, and
- technical terminology.

In contrast, *Therova (2020)* divides the vocabulary into four subgroups and gives the following description for each:

- *high-frequency words* (include a large number of texts also found in all types of language usage);
- *technical words* (cover a specific topic or subject);
- *low-frequency words* (used rarely and not found in a large number of texts);

- *and academic words* (refer to a large number of academic texts and are not typical of non-academic texts).

In the table below the most common terms shall be reviewed:

Methodology.

Term	Meaning	Linguist/Year	Contains	Includes
GSL	The General Service	West, 1953.	2,000 word families	Most frequently used words
AVL	The Academic Vocabulary List	Gardner & Davies, 2013	3,015 core academic words (lemmas) / 120 million words	Academic words derived from the Corpus of Contemporary American English (COCA)
AWL	The Academic Word List	Coxhead, 2000	570 word families	Words used with great frequency in many academic texts.
AKL	<i>Academic Keyword List</i>	Paquot, 2010	-	Both academic and general words.
OPAL	Oxford Phrasal Academic Lexicon	McCarthy, 2019	6,000 common American and British Phrasal verbs	Most significant words and phrases for learners of English in academic discourse.

Coxhead (2011) indicates other 4 principles of word selection for inclusion in AVL. However, the author questions the first of these, which is '*the 2,000 most frequent word families of West's (1953) General Service List of English Words (GSL)*' (*Coxhead, 2011*). Suggesting that the aim of learning academic English is not general English, Coxhead puts forward 3 other principles:

- *frequency* (word families are found 100 times or more in each of the four subjects of the corpus);
- *range* (in 15 or more of the topics);
- *uniformity* (over 10 times in the four disciplines).

West (1953 cited in Charles & Pecorari, 2016) compiled the so-called General Service List of English Words (GSL). Criteria that were important considerations in compiling this list were:

- frequency of usage,
- usage range,
- necessity to learn and
- ease of learning.

Technical terminology covers narrowly focused or subject areas such as microbiology, bioengineering, etc. Numerous methods, including:

- rating scales,
- computer-based techniques; and

- systematic classification has been used to define these words.

The article by Charles & Pecorari (2016) reports the number of academic words in the text as 14% of total number of words, whereas Coxhead (2011) speaks about 10%.

The academic vocabulary is used in academic discourse and with less frequency compared to general English. The knowledge of the Academic Word List (AWL) is of great importance to students, as it occurs in lectures, articles and books that they have to deal with. To be defined as an academic word it must be used *less frequently than the general vocabulary*. What distinguishes it from technical terminology is that academic words *occur in more than one subject or area*. Masrai & Milton (2018) referring to Hyland & Tse (2007) describe the difference between general and academic vocabulary stating that “many AVL words are polysemantic and have broad applications in language. Language learners may be familiar with one of its meanings without knowing its meaning and usage in an academic context.”

Reviewed articles demonstrate that linguists such as Therova (2020) and Hartshorn & Hart (2016) also make a distinction between AVL and AWL, suggesting that AVL is more academic and sophisticated. In her article *Therova (2020)* divides academic word lists into two large groups:

- those that are compilations of academic vocabulary found in different academic subject areas (i.e., general academic word lists);
- those including academic vocabulary found in specific academic disciplines (i.e., discipline-specific word lists).

According to *Coxhead (2011)* AWL is classified into 10 sub-lists. The author suggests that the first sub-list includes the 60 most frequently occurring word families in the Academic Word List, the second sub-list includes the following 60 most frequently occurring word families, and etc,

Conclusion.

In the articles under consideration, linguists describe in detail the reasons why students learning English need to know academic vocabulary. They cite various figures to support their words:

Charles & Pecorari (2016), citing Hu & Nation (2000), Laufer & Ravenhorst-Kalovski (2010) suggest that a reader must know between 95 per cent and 98 per cent of words to be able to reach full understanding. This proves the necessity of teaching the academic vocabulary to the students, whatever the name of the vocabulary may be (AWL, AVL, AKL). The instructors' role is to find the right teaching method, to select the appropriate word list for the course, and to focus on it. In this case, they must be guided by the needs of the students and the purpose of the course being taught.

Apparently, as this paper shows, the academic word list is updated from time to time with new words. This is facilitated by various factors. It follows that teachers should pay attention to the relevance and novelty of the work.

Reference:

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